

Dedication to Nina Thornhill

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Abstract: I met Nina during my MSc at Imperial College London. After finishing the MSc, she offered me a PhD position, and during these last years, I obtained the knowledge and skills that will help me build my future. Her presence in my life has helped me in my academic and personal life, and I wanted to express my sincere gratitude to the effort Nina put on me.

Keywords: Imperial College London, ABB, PhD, MSc, Supervisor.

Nina Thornhill has been an inspiration in my academic and my personal life.

My stay in London started five years ago. I was going to start my master degree, and I was anxious about my new situation: a new city, and a new language. My lack of confidence made me struggled to establish new relationships. Then I had to choose a project for the MSc programme, and consequently, a supervisor. That is when I met Nina.

During the very first moments of our conversation, I was nervous to the point that I could not stop stuttering. However, Nina patiently listened to everything I said. For the first time in London, I could express my ideas without the fear of being judged.

Nina slowly helped me build up my confidence, and her infinite patience and dedication were the components that encouraged me to overcome the upcoming obstacles. Even though she was always busy, Nina never doubted in doing as much as possible for supporting me. That perseverance helped me make the most of the year, and I ended the master degree as a new person, with more ambitions and eager to learn more.

I finished my master degree, but our history had not ended. Nina offered me a PhD position in collaboration with ABB. She and John Pretlove interviewed me to occupy the vacancy. When our meeting concluded, I was sure that I was not going to receive the role. Nina, however, trusted me, and I received an email saying that the position was mine. I could never be grateful enough for that opportunity.

When I started the PhD, I thought that everything I was going to learn belonged to the academic field. Nevertheless, Nina made sure that I could develop every aspect needed in the academic and non-academic areas. Nina taught me that the way I communicated went far beyond equations and technical text. Thanks to that, I was able to deliver presentations and enjoy doing it.

Thanks to Nina, I could attend my first conference that took place in Denmark. I could also work in the ABB's facilities in Oslo, and I was able to visit the city. However, without a doubt, the trip that I will never forget is the one we made to Hammerfest, Norway. In Hammerfest, we could visit Equinor's liquefied natural gas plant. The memory of the industrial site surrounded by the breathtaking landscape was only possible

due to the trust Nina had in me when she accepted me as a PhD student.

The approach Nina had to educate always fascinated me. She gave me the freedom to choose the procedure for tackling problems, and then she adapted to the method I chose. Nina never ceased to learn new strategies and was committed to following the methodology that I preferred to help me improve it. In my opinion, a great educator has to thrive for what Nina has done with me: she let me choose the road, and then she gave me the vehicle for reaching the goal.

These five years were the most exciting and fruitful years of my life, and Nina played a vital role during this period. I am taking my first steps into the work environment, and all the knowledge I gathered is a result of the hard work Nina has deposited on me.

For all these reasons, Nina Thornhill has been an inspiration in my academic and my personal life.